

Utilisation of cupric engulfment by *Escherichia coli* for PcoC (a superoxide dismutase) induction

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Abstract : Cu has been used as an inducer of PcoC (SOD) in *E. coli* to screen the time for achieving maximum activity. This SOD can be isolated from bacterial system and purified to serve as a source for use in medicines for humans since SOD proteins of humans and *E. coli* share significant sequence similarity. Copper engulfment capacity of *E. coli* has been utilised to induce PcoC (SOD) which has been measured by estimating the activity of the two proteins, PcoA and PcoC (Pco stands for plasmid borne copper resistance operon) with variation in concentration of Cu^{II} in the medium and duration of incubation. Cu^{II} engulfment capacity of *E. coli* through liposome is greater in case of PcoC than PcoA.

Keywords : *E. coli*, PcoC, cupric engulfment, induction, PcoA.

Introduction

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) is one kind of metalloenzyme that catalyses the formation of hydrogen peroxide and oxygen from superoxide and thus protects against superoxide induced damage. It can be used in antioxidization, fight against senium and improve immunological function. SOD can be used in health care like osteoarthritis, periodontal use, food, cosmetics and beer. SOD compounds are used as main material in producing high-tech new drugs against cancer, for reducing blood pressure and reducing blood fat. Human SOD derived from recombinant microorganisms is being developed to explore its therapeutic potential particularly in ischemia-reperfusion damage, adult respiratory distress or similar conditions¹.

E. coli, being friendly intestinal bacteria may serve as the source for the SOD which is also known as PcoC (Pco stands for plasmid borne copper resistance operon). Induction of SOD can be done by incubating *E. coli* cells with medium containing CuSO₄ or liposome mediated Cu^{II} entry.

Recently, liposomes have been studied a lot for establishing delivery of substances across the plasma membrane. Liposomes are closed, spherical, bi-layered and formed by lipid molecules. They form spontaneously and have an asymmetric distribution of polymer chains between the inner and outer monolayers. Liposome mediated Cu^{II} entry has been utilized to avoid unwanted side effects.

Cu^{II} at low concentration act as micronutrient but at high concentration is toxic for cell. PcoA and PcoC are present to enable *E. coli* cells to survive high concentration of Cu^{II}. Excess Cu is harmful to bacteria and is expelled out of the cell with the help of PcoA and PcoC. PcoC activity increases in liposome mediated entry of Cu^{II}. PcoC has been taken into consideration owing to its medicinal value so that it may be isolated from *E. coli* after treatment of the cells with Cu^{II} upto certain time period for attaining maximum activity. PcoA is not affected by liposome mediated Cu^{II} entry whereas PcoC activity is influenced by liposome mediated Cu^{II} entry.

PcoC may serve as a factor to present copper to PcoA (CueO or copper export oxidase) or to escort copper out of the cell. PcoA (565 amino acids) and PcoC (103 amino acids) are two soluble periplasmic proteins². PcoA is not indispensable for cell but PcoC is indispensable for cell³.

Mechanisms proposed for copper efflux include – complexation, reduced accumulation, extracellular complexation and sequestration in periplasm⁴.

The Cu hypersensitive phenotype of pcoC null cells indicates that PcoC proteins work within a biochemical pathway which involves a partnership with the protein encoded by PcoA⁵.

The main objective of the study was to observe the induction of cupric Cu^{II} engulfment by growing *E. coli* cells in medium containing Cu^{II} and by liposome mediated delivery of Cu^{II} to *E. coli* cells with variations in concentration of Cu^{II} and duration of incubation.

Materials and methods :

(A) *Sequence alignment of human and E. coli SOD* : ClustalW2 (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/clustalw2/index.html>) was used to find the protein sequence homology between human and *E. coli* SOD.

(B) *Isolation and harvesting of pure cultures of E. coli cells* : This was the first method that was adopted and was done very cautiously because any contamination would hamper readings taken later during assay. The lactose broth (50 mL) was prepared and tap water was inoculated into it. The media was incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Lactose broth (50 mL) was prepared and tap water was inoculated into it. Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar was prepared and was streaked with a loop full of culture from the above solution. Incubation was done at 37 °C for 24 h. Isolated, nucleated colonies obtained on EMB plates were identified as *E. coli* and subcultured for all later uses.

(C) *Rapid, simple and quantitative release of periplasmic proteins* : Periplasmic proteins were isolated using the method of Prody *et al.*⁶. 2 ml bacterial cultures were grown to saturation overnight in culture tubes. Cells were collected by centrifugation for 10 min at 1100xg. Supernatant was decanted thoroughly. Cell pellet was resuspended by brief vortexing in the residual medium. 20 µl of chloroform was added. After brief vortexing, the tubes were maintained at room temperature for about 15 min. 0.2 ml

of 0.01 M Tris Hydrochloride (pH 8) was added. The cells were separated by centrifugation at 6000xg for 20 min and supernatant fraction containing the periplasmic proteins was withdrawn with a pasteur pipette.

The following parameters were standardised like the pH, concentration of Cu^{II} and the duration of incubation. The pH selected was 5.5 since above this pH Cu precipitates as hydroxides. The concentration of Cu^{II} chosen was 0.1, 0.25, 0.75 mM as *E. coli* did not grow above 0.75 mM. Duration of incubation chosen was 24, 48 and 72 h as cell number dropped after this and growth more than 96 h led to undesired contamination. Controls with no Cu were maintained through out the experiment. Moreover activity of the PcoA and PcoC proteins of *E. coli* were compared under the following two conditions :

(i) *E. coli* grown in culture media in which copper sulphate had been directly added to maintain desired concentrations of 0.1, 0.25 and 0.75 mM Cu^{II}.

(ii) *E. coli* grown in culture media containing liposomes, which themselves act as carrier vesicles for Cu^{II}.

Thus nutrient broths at constant pH 5.5, containing above mentioned three concentrations of Cu^{II} were inoculated with pure cultures of *E. coli*, either by direct addition of CuSO₄ or by liposomes mediated Cu^{II} delivery. These were incubated for 24, 48 and 72 h respectively before estimating the activity of PcoA and PcoC proteins.

(D) *Estimation of PcoA protein activity or multicopper oxidase activity assay* : PcoA activity was measured by the method of Lehmann *et al.*⁷. The activity assay were performed aerobically utilising 3,3-dimethoxy benzidine or *ortho* anisidine as the colorimetric indicator for oxidase activity at 25 °C. In this assay 15 µl of periplasmic extract was combined with 225 µl of 0.1 M sodium acetate (pH 5.5). The reaction was initiated by the addition of 60 µl of 7.88 mM 3,3-dimethoxy benzidine, alternatively *ortho* anisidine. Reactions were performed in duplicate for each assay. Reactions were stopped at 5 min and 120 min respectively, by the addition of 600 µl of 18 N H₂SO₄ to each reaction. The difference in absorbance at 540 nm between the 120 min and 5 min action was used to calculate the amount of oxidised substrate.

(E) *Estimation of PcoC protein activity* : PcoC was assayed following method of Roth *et al.*⁸. For this purpose, 0.1 ml of 1 mM diethylene tri-amine penta-acetate

(DTPA) was mixed with 1.8 ml of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5). To this, 0.01 ml of periplasmic extract was added. 99 µl of pyrogallol (2.6 mM in 10 mM HCl) was added to the previous mixture. Reading was taken at 420 nm for spectrophotometric analysis.

(F) *Protein estimation by Folin-Lowry method*⁹ : Protein was measured spectrophotometrically at 660 nm.

(G) *Preparation of liposomes* : Liposomes were prepared following standard procedure. Pure castor oil was aseptically mixed with 70% ethyl alcohol at 1 : 5 ratio respectively. Copper sulfate solution of desired concentration was prepared and warmed. Inside the Laminar Air Flow, the oil-alcohol mixture was aseptically and slowly injected into the warm aqueous solution, at 1 : 4 ratio respectively. This resulted in osmotically active, unilamellar vesicles, which can be observed under the microscope.

Results and discussion

Alignment of human SOD with *E. coli* SOD using ClustalW 2.0.1 multiple sequence alignment program showed that human SOD is ~41% similar in protein sequence with *E. coli* SOD.

Fig. 1. Alignment of human SOD with *E. coli* SOD using ClustalW 2.0.1 multiple sequence alignment program (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/clustalw2/index.html>). Shaded using GeneDoc Version 2.7.000¹⁰. Human SOD is ~41% similar in protein sequence with *E. coli* SOD.

The specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoA and PcoC was plotted against number of days in the X-axis when *E. coli* cells were treated with medium containing 0.1, 0.25 and 0.75 mM CuSO₄ as well as liposomes containing the similar concentrations of Cu^{II} ions.

For the activity of PcoA protein : For liposome mediated induction, no activity has been observed on day 1, in case of all the given concentrations, 0.1, 0.25, 0.75 mM (Figs. 2a, 2b and 2c). In this case, activity of the protein PcoA reaches a peak on day 2 and then comes down gradually again (Figs. 2a, 2b and 2c). This trait has been

observed for all the concentrations as well. Activity of the protein in direct CuSO₄ containing media is always higher than the liposome mediated induction system.

For direct CuSO₄ containing media, in case of 0.25 and 0.75 mM concentrations, the activity of PcoA rises from day 1 to day 2, reaches a peak and then comes down gradually with day 3 again (Figs. 2b and 2c). In case of 0.1 mM, the activity of PcoA goes on increasing even till day 3 (Fig. 2a).

For the activity of PcoC protein : Strikingly, it was observed that liposome mediated induction could trigger on the activity of PcoC right from day 1, unlike PcoA (Figs. 3b and 3c). But the activity increases from day 2 in case of 0.1 mM Cu^{II} concentration and decreases on day 3 (Fig. 3a). The PcoC activity increase in case of 0.1 mM Cu^{II} is less compared to the other two concentrations.

In case of 0.25 and 0.75 mM concentration, liposome mediated induction could give more activity than direct CuSO₄ containing media on the second day of incubation (Figs. 3b and 3c). These concentrations can be utilised to isolate PcoC for purification.

PcoA activity : After analysing the graphical results, the following points of observation can be noted for the PcoA activity. It can be inferred from the above bar diagrams of PcoA (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2c) that greater amount of Cu^{II} enters the cells when they are incubated in a CuSO₄ containing media than through liposome mediation. This may result due to less chance of fusion of liposomes to the protective Lipo-polysaccharide outer membranes of *E. coli* cells. It was also seen that with increasing days, activity of the PcoA protein comes down. In addition, the activity of PcoA was found to be directly proportional to

Fig. 2a. Specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoA (Y-axis) at 0.1 mM Cu^{II} (CuSO₄) with number of days (X-axis) : Lighter shaded bar represents treatment with 0.25 mM CuSO₄ and darker shaded bar represents treatment with liposome containing 0.25 mM CuSO₄.

Fig. 3a. Specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoC (Y-axis) at 0.1 mM Cu^{II} (CuSO₄) with number of days (X-axis) : Lighter shaded bar represents treatment with 0.1 mM CuSO₄ and darker shaded bar represents treatment with liposome containing 0.1 mM CuSO₄.

Fig. 2b. Specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoA (Y-axis) at 0.25 mM Cu^{II} (CuSO₄) with number of days (X-axis) : Lighter shaded bar represents treatment with 0.25 mM CuSO₄ and darker shaded bar represents treatment with liposome containing 0.25 mM CuSO₄.

Fig. 3b. Specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoC (Y-axis) at 0.25 mM Cu^{II} (CuSO₄) with number of days (X-axis) : Lighter shaded bar represents treatment with 0.25 mM CuSO₄ and darker shaded bar represents treatment with liposome containing 0.25 mM CuSO₄.

Fig. 2c. Specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoA (Y-axis) at 0.75 mM Cu^{II} (CuSO₄) with number of days (X-axis) : Lighter shaded bar represents treatment with 0.75 mM CuSO₄ and darker shaded bar represents treatment with liposome containing 0.75 mM CuSO₄.

Fig. 3c. Specific activity (units/mg/min) of PcoC (Y-axis) at 0.75 mM Cu^{II} (CuSO₄) with number of days (X-axis) : Lighter shaded bar represents treatment with 0.75 mM CuSO₄ and darker shaded bar represents treatment with liposome containing 0.75 mM CuSO₄.

the concentrations of Cu^{II}. As more Cu^{II} entered the cell, more of PcoA was synthesised to save the cell from harmful effects.

PcoC activity : It seems from the above bar diagrams (Figs. 3a, 3b, 3c), PcoC's role in effluxing Cu^{II} from the

cell is more vital PcoA. Activity of SOD reaches maximum at the second day in both conditions. This system is seemingly much more sensitive and even minute quantities of Cu^{II} influx can turn it on.

Copper entrapment study reveals that *E. coli* possess

maximum PcoC activity at second day after treatment with liposome mediated Cu^{II} entry. Liposome has been used for easy delivery of Cu^{II} into the cell and to eliminate unnecessary side effects. So it can be suggested that SOD can be isolated from *E. coli* on second day of treatment with 0.25 and 0.75 mM Cu^{II} with liposome because of higher activity of SOD. This SOD can be purified and utilised for medicinal purposes.

Conclusion : The main importance of the whole study is that the copper engulfment procedures may be utilized for inducing PcoC (SOD) and this SOD having medicinal significance can then be purified from *E. coli* for use in drugs for humans since human SOD is ~41% similar in protein sequence with *E. coli* SOD.

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